

TITLE

From relaxation to buckling: A continuum elastic framework connecting surface instabilities of highly compressed lipid thin films

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ABSTRACT

Self-assembled thin films can undergo different reversible collapse modes that are critical to regulate their function in both biology and technology. Langmuir trough compression experiments show that out-of-plane buckling (e.g., folding) and in-plane relaxation (e.g., the re-organization of lipid domains) in highly compressed lipid monolayers can be tuned via altering monolayer softness. Yet, a unified mechanistic understanding of how in-plane relaxation occurs and how it is distinguished from folding remains elusive. Here, we use continuum mechanics, finite element simulations, and Langmuir trough data to elucidate the underlying mechanism that can connect these instability modes. We show that modeling highly compressed lipid monolayers as thin, elastic sheets with the ability to release in-plane compressive load through in-plane shear localization (shear banding) triggers monolayer in-plane relaxation. Tuning this relaxation in our model demonstrates a great capability to switch between different instability modes. We further perform rigorous comparisons between a realistic heterogeneous model built from FM images of lipid monolayers and experimental data by analyzing the morphology of lipid domains. Results show a strong correlation between the presence of shear banding and the degree of domain re-organization. Without this ability to trigger strain localization, the model produces the morphological features that are observed in folding lipid monolayers. Our findings could lead to a universal framework to unify all observed monolayer instabilities that will enable the effective control of both microscopic structure (morphology and arrangement of self-assembled molecules) and continuum structure (mechanical stability).

SIGNIFICANCE

Using lipid monolayers as a representative system to study self-assembled thin solid films, this work develops a new approach that integrates elastic models with an in-plane relaxation mechanism driven by shear banding to, for the first time, distinguish between folding and in-plane relaxing morphologies in finite element numerical simulations. This work proposes a general elastic framework that underlies the numerous surface instabilities in Langmuir monolayers and can be extended to many other material systems including 2D materials, thin sheets, self-organizing matters, and active solids. Furthermore, as lipid interfaces are critical for biological and mechanical functionalities in living systems from cells to organisms, this work can be applied to other fields to substantially increase our current understanding of living matters.

INTRODUCTION

Thin films formed by the self-assembly of molecules at the air-liquid interface are prevalent in both biological and technological material systems. Their critical ability to regulate surface tension has been exploited in various structures including those associated with drug delivery (1–3), coatings in medical devices (4–7), electronic materials (8–11), and biological interfaces (12–16) to maintain interfacial structural stability in response to mechanical forces. Thus, Langmuir monolayers on air-liquid interfaces have been used extensively in biophysics, biochemistry, and nanotechnology fields as a model system to probe surface tension regulation and monolayer response to applied forces (17–20). A large body of work has been conducted on the liquid-liquid 2D phase transitions and morphologies of soft self-assembled thin sheets (18, 21–26). At this stage, the sheet exhibits a dominant fluid-like state with phase transitions governed by thermodynamic laws. At high levels of compression, a fluid-like sheet can evolve into a solid-like sheet, which has also been examined in previous studies (27, 28). The critical difference between a liquid and a solid is the ability to support static shear stress (29, 30). While liquids can easily relax such stresses through viscous dissipation, solids cannot, giving rise to the various surface instabilities studied in thin solid films. It is well-known that self-assembled thin sheets respond to high compressive forces with different modes of surface instabilities, the mechanical reversibility of which being an important factor in maintaining surface tension (31–42). Nevertheless, the underlying mechanism that dictates and unifies these modes in monolayers is far less understood.

Lipid monolayers are one experimental example of a thin sheet that undergoes phase transitions and instabilities in response to lateral compression (21, 32, 38). Biologically relevant in the eyes, ears, and lungs, the ability of these sheets to undergo reversible collapse and maintain mechanical stability is integral to their biological function/dysfunction and to the development of related medical treatments (12–16). Under unilateral compression in a Langmuir trough, both out-of-

plane buckling and in-plane relaxation have been observed experimentally in highly compressed lipid monolayers. Yet, current mechanistic understanding of the correlation between these instability modes is lacking. In this work, we hypothesize that highly compressed lipid monolayers can be represented as elastic sheets where in-plane relaxation is triggered by the monolayer's ability to develop in-plane shear localization (shear banding). This hypothesis is tested via development of new modeling for lipid monolayers validated against Langmuir trough experimental data where shear banding serves as a mechanism differentiating out-of-plane folding and in-plane relaxation.

Experimental instability in lipid monolayers:

Prior to applying mechanical forces via the unilateral compression in a Langmuir trough (Fig 1A), confluent lipid monolayers begin as a homogeneous fluid material. Under increasing compression, the monolayer becomes highly heterogeneous with condensed lipid domains (dark) of approximately 10 μm in diameter dispersed in a soft matrix (light) (Fig. 1B). Fluorescence microscopy (FM) and surface tensiometry are experimental techniques with which the monolayer multi-scale response to compression can be probed, such as the molecular phase transition from gas, to liquid-like, to solid-like (22, 43, 44) and surface instabilities (32). In solid lipid monolayers, reversible out-of-plane instabilities (Fig. 1C) such as crumpling (out-of-plane buckling with point and line singularities) and folding (localized but smooth out-of-plane buckling that is dominated by bending and stretching) are widely presented in the literature (39, 45–48). Recently, a new mode of instability where the lipid monolayers relax in-plane leading to a banding morphology of condensed domains was discovered (Fig. 1C) (37, 39). Interestingly, all of these solid instabilities resemble well-known problems in traditional solid-mechanics, including buckling of confined thin films (40, 46, 49), crumpling of thin sheets (50, 51), and shear banding in granular materials (Fig. 1C) (52–54).

Experiments have shown that tuning the softness of the lipid monolayers by modifying lipid composition or temperature can tune collapse phenomena (39, 55–57). A general phase diagram showing the existence of out-of-plane folding/crumpling and in-plane relaxation in various tunable lipid monolayer systems has been reported in the literature (37, 39). As one such example, the lipid mixture DPPC:POPG 7:3 at 25C is observed to exhibit folding. This mixture is shown to soften through two ways: 1) at the same 25C temperature but with the addition of the peptide SP-B 9-25 or 2) same mixture at 32C temperature. Both methods of softening allow in-plane relaxation via domain reorganization. For the purpose of characterizing this tunability and comparing folding to in-plane relaxation, we bring to focus existing FM micrographs from DPPC:POPG 7:3 at 25C, with and without addition of peptide (Fig 2), as published in Pocivavsek, et al. *Soft Matter* (2008) (37). Fig. 2 shows the differing morphologies of these two compositions of lipid monolayer at two points: 1) start of the elastic regime, before relaxation (low lateral pressure) and 2) after relaxation (high lateral pressure). The organization of the condensed domains is used to probe how the matrix is relaxing at the continuum scale and an observed morphological difference between folding and in-plane relaxation systems suggests a difference in matrix relaxation. The defining characteristic of in-plane relaxation in lipid monolayers is the domain packing change from roughly hexagonal packing or powder structure to a banded morphology. This feature is not observed in lipid monolayers that fold, where the same powder structure morphology persists. To quantify this feature globally, past work has conducted Fourier transforms of 2D autocorrelations of FM images (37). In this work, we focus on smaller scale local morphologies, and quantitatively characterize this feature using 2D autocorrelations alone, as described in the methods, showcasing example local morphologies in Fig 2.

Folding in thin elastic sheets has been interpreted as a mechanism to release in-plane compressive loading. This mechanism also provides good explanation for the development of large amplitude folds of micron size observed in lipid and other self-assembled (e.g, nanoparticles) monolayers with nanometer scale thickness. The ability of domains to break the symmetry of their hexagonal packing and reorganize in-plane into bands suggests the need to explore another mechanism that the lipid monolayer may undergo to relax in-plane loading. In addition, the tunability of this relaxation in many diverse lipid compositions indicates a universality of the underlying mechanisms for the different modes of lipid monolayer instability. Currently, these aspects are poorly understood and no current work has shed significant insights into the differences in experimental observations as presented in Fig 2.

Figure 1. Experimental method and motivation for understanding lipid monolayer surface instabilities. A) Schematic for the experimental setup of a Langmuir trough as utilized to capture all FM images within this text. B) Surface pressure measured through surface tensiometer as the difference between surface tension of lipid-free and lipid-covered interface and different phases and transitions captured with FM during compression using the Langmuir trough setup. C) Three typical modes of out-of-plane and in-plane instabilities in lipid monolayers and corresponding modes of instability well-known in solid mechanics: buckling of confined thin films (40), crumpling of thin sheets, and shear banding in granular materials (54).

Figure 2. Evolutions of the morphology of condensed domain (dark ovals in the images) organization captured by FM images for monolayers that fold, DPPC:POPG 7:3 at 25C (left) and relax in-plane, DPPC:POPG 7:3 plus 2 mol% SP-B 9-25 peptide (right) at low (top, 30mN m⁻¹ surface pressure) and high (bottom, 70mN m⁻¹) compression, as previously published (37). 2D image autocorrelations show that for folding lipid monolayers, the nearly hexagonal packing of the condensed domains is maintained with increasing lateral compression prior to the out-of-plane instability (the filled red areas in the 2D autocorrelations (right) of the left column show similar powder like structures). For in-plane relaxing monolayers, the nearly hexagonal packing of condensed domains also exists at low compression but is disturbed at high compression where distinct bands of condensed domains are emphasized in the 2D image correlation analysis (the filled red areas in the 2D autocorrelations of the right column show a powder like structure at low compression, while distinct lines are shown at high compression).

Modeling instability in lipid monolayers:

Many theoretical and computational approaches to study lipid monolayers take place at the molecular level. Incorporating thermodynamics principles, where equations of state and defects were used to describe the phase transition in lipid monolayers (20-22), folding onset was captured by minimizing the interfacial energy. MD simulations show the appearance of undulations followed by the transition to a single fold into the aqueous sub-phase upon increasing lateral compression (41, 58, 59). Yet, the simulated undulation and fold are on the order of lipid monolayer thickness due to the limited size (nanometer) of these simulations. Thus, while providing valuable insights into molecular interactions that underlie the onset of out-of-plane instabilities, these approaches have not successfully explained the three order of magnitude difference in the fold length scale (micron) as compared to thickness (nanometer). Alternative studies that utilize a continuum mechanics approach were proposed to quantitatively characterize folding of both lipid and gold nanoparticle films (40, 46, 49, 60, 61). The Langmuir monolayer is considered as a uniform elastic plate that buckles under lateral compression. A simple model was developed by Ries for solid-like response of highly compressed monolayers where the hypothesis of elastic plate buckling is used to explain the appearance of a tall fold atop of the monolayer (46). The wrinkle-to-fold model further extends this assumption to study the peculiar folding behavior in monolayers of lipid and gold nanoparticles (40). It shows that the films go through wrinkling with micron-size wavelength determined by the relative stiffness of the monolayer and the liquid sub-phase. Under further compression, these wrinkles localize into large folds observed experimentally. Thus, this reduced geometric approach can provide a highly quantitative mechanistic understanding of experimental observations.

Relatively fewer efforts have focused on modeling in-plane relaxation in lipid monolayers. Some studies suggest the similarity with flow induced shear bands in complex fluids and granular materials (62–64). Other recent attempts aim to enrich material models by extending the success of modeling folding lipid monolayers as homogeneous elastic plates to in-plane relaxation. As folding monolayers can be described with neo-Hookean and other hyperelastic equations (40, 46), these works explore new constitutive equations to see if they can give rise to in-plane relaxation. Specifically, models that invoke either irreversibility either through inelastic material behavior (e.g., viscoelastic, plastic) or nonlinear elasticity with arbitrary two-slopes stiffnesses (e.g., bi-elastic) were discussed (39).

A completely different approach assumes that the lipid monolayer mechanically behaves like a generic hyperelastic material, storing elastic energy both through local volume and shape changes of the continuum at hand (65). Through an incremental approach to nonlinear elasticity, there the onset for the occurrence of shear band bifurcations was fully characterized, giving then sufficient conditions on the above mentioned energy for such bifurcations to occur. This new result is independent on the particular choice of the energy itself, hence it is very powerful and paves the way to more specific choices of the monolayer's response.

In particular, informed by experimental isotherms of such monolayers, (65) further explored the consequences of choosing a hyperfoam-like energetics. Among other features, by looking at the corresponding isotherms, such a hyperfoam model allows for replicating the observed hardening during the densification phases before encountering a point of instability. This work analytically established the fact that shear banding turns out to be a material instability on the nonlinear elastic response of the continuum representing the lipid monolayer, providing in-plane relaxation of the material response. Despite of the generality of the obtained result in (65), the particular chosen energetics, namely the hyperfoam model, is highly complex and, by utilizing that in a Finite Element Analysis (FEA), the model parameters were difficult to control. This made that hard to computationally interpret how shear banding develops and numerically correlates with in-plane relaxation. Despite the efforts provided through the thorough analysis of that hyperfoam model, although part of the experimentally observed isotherms were reproduced, no successful quantitative comparisons between the resulting FEA simulations with experimentally observed morphology (Fig. 2) were achieved. This emphasizes the current lack of understanding of what specific macroscopic constitutive nonlinear elastic response would fully reproduce isotherms and predict the fine geometry of the lipid monolayers driving the mechanisms that promote in-plane relaxation.

In spite of the new and general results obtained in (65), the tunable nature of experimental lipid monolayer instabilities further necessitates the development of a new computational model with an appropriate macroscopic constitutive equation to describe lipid monolayers. The resulting computational analyses have to fully capture the distinct experimental observation of domain morphology in both folding and in-plane relaxing lipid monolayers. It is worth remarking that, whenever shear bands are observed in a two-phase continuum, one may hypothesize that the in-plane reorganization of domains (phase 1) is due to the ability of the matrix (phase 2) to release compressive load via regions of highly localized shear strain, or shear bands. Here, we first establish a very specific constitutive hyperelastic model that can tune between strong, weak, and no shear banding. Independent of the particular choice of the hyperelastic energy chosen to reproduce the lipid monolayer's response, the ability to trigger or not trigger shear banding in the material model is assumed to be associated with the ability of the lipid monolayer to undergo in-plane or out-of-plane instability, respectively. We further explore these instability modes through modeling thin sheet instabilities in response to lateral compression via FEA. We start with a homogeneous representation of lipid monolayers, then enrich the modeling with the heterogeneous domain morphology captured in FM imaging. We then perform a rigorous comparison between FE modeling and experimental data to further test our hypothesis. Our aim is to unify all observed monolayer instabilities through a generalized macroscopic elastic framework validated against experimental FM images.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tunable FE model for in-plane relaxation in lipid monolayers

Building upon the success of previous hyperelastic approaches to capture folding, in this Section, we hypothesize that lipid monolayers and the various observed instability modes can be described by a general material model based on a hyperelastic energy function. We test this by first establishing a tunable constitutive material and developing

understanding of how in-plane relaxation occurs first in a homogeneous representation of lipid monolayers, then extending it to characterize the resultant material deformations in realistic heterogeneous lipid monolayers.

Figure 3. Tuning shear band onset and behavior in a homogeneous model. The top row of plots presents analytical solutions for shear stress vs. shear strain in the case of simple shear (schematic top left), from Eq 14 in the Appendix. The inset figures depict loss of ellipticity analysis for a unilateral compression (schematic middle left) from Eq 6, which leads to the determination of the critical value of the nominal stretch λ_N , at which shear bands occur. Analytical predictions show no relaxation onset for Case 1 and onsets of relaxation for the last two cases, as concluded from Case 1 showing a monotonic stress-strain response, Case 2 showing the shear stress σ drops when the shear strain $\gamma_s = \gamma_{s,c}$ but quickly increases again, and Case 3 showing σ drops when $\gamma_s = \gamma_{s,c}$. The neo-Hookean material used successfully to study folding is also presented in the plot of Case 1, showing the great capability to tune this material model. The bottom row of plots shows the corresponding FE solutions for a unilateral compression of a homogenous model (schematic bottom left) where the onset of shear banding is associated with the peak in aggregate reaction force. Note the good agreement of λ_N , (corresponding star symbols in inset vs bottom row) between the two approaches for all three cases. Inset in each plot are representative shear strain heat maps for the FE model over the course of compression. A homogeneous deformation field is maintained in Case 1. In Case 2, shear bands form and become more dilute when the stress-strain becomes monotonic again. Lastly, in Case 3, sharp shear bands occur and persist over the entire simulation.

Non-monotonic hyperelastic material model allows for in-plane relaxation via the formation of shear bands: homogeneous representation of lipid monolayers.

In continuum mechanics, a 2D shear band can be characterized mathematically as an area, surrounded by shocklines, where the shear strain is significantly higher than outside, leading to the majority of the shear deformation localizing within the shear band (53). This redistribution of strain allows for in-plane relaxation. Thus, we first enrich the current hyperelastic model for folding lipid monolayers with this capacity to relax in-plane compressive load, testing whether it can provide a tunable constitutive model for both in-plane and out-of-plane instabilities in lipid monolayers. While the

field of continuum mechanics provides multiple modeling approaches for shear banding, there has only been very limited theoretical work put towards applying shear banding to lipid monolayers (65). Even so, no model has yet captured the change in lipid monolayer morphology associated with in-plane relaxation. In this work, with the goal to propose a simple, tunable constitutive model, we adapt an existing material model developed by Seki and Alturi (66). This model is previously used only for mathematical and computational problems; here we develop a new understanding for its application in lipid monolayers, emphasizing the feature that we hypothesize governs the mechanism for in-plane relaxation. The response from this model described by an incompressible hyperelastic-type energy function (see details in the Method Section) is dictated by 3 material properties: (C_1, C_2, C_3) where C_1 controls the first elastic regime, C_2 controls the relaxation regime, and C_3 controls the second elastic regime, further discussed in Appendix 2 and shown in Fig S1. The influence of the corresponding response on shear banding onset is also analyzed by the standard loss of ellipticity analysis in continuum mechanics (analytical approach) utilized to determine if shear strain localization occurs (see Method section and Appendix 3). In this work, with a focus on shear banding tunability of this model as an underlying mechanism for different instability modes, we showcase here (Fig 3) three typical cases: (Case 1: $C_1=1, C_2=5, C_3=0.5$; Case 2: $C_1=1, C_2=5, C_3=0.1$; Case 3: $C_1=1, C_2=10, C_3=0.001$) and analyze shear banding of the corresponding constitutive model. The first case shows a monotonic response indicating no ability to shear band. Note that the typical neo-Hookean case used to model folding lipid monolayers is also obtained from this model with appropriate specifications of $(C_1=1, C_2=0, C_3=0)$. The last two cases exhibit non-monotonic shear stress-shear strain response in simple shear (Fig 3 top row), which creates the desired shear banding phenomena, where the point of shear stress relaxation in simple shear can be considered as the critical point of shear band onset (see Method Section).

To better associate shear banding induced by unilateral compression in Langmuir trough experimentation with the corresponding constitutive behaviors of lipid monolayers described by these three cases, we utilize a homogeneous FE model as described in the methods. We characterize the effective behavior of the material through recording the aggregate reaction force along one vertical boundary as a function of nominal stretch, $\lambda_N = L/L_0$, where L and L_0 are the deformed and undeformed width of the FE model, respectively. The point where reaction force drops is the critical nominal stretch, or $\lambda_{N,C}$. As described in Appendix 3 and shown in Fig 3, this computational critical point agrees with the analytical onset of relaxation as determined from the loss of ellipticity analysis, suggesting that shear banding onset is captured well by both analyses. For the parameter sets that do not analytically provide a relaxation point, such as Case 1 and neo-Hookean, plotted in Fig 3, the resultant computational result shows no drop in reaction force. The consistent agreement between analytical and FE model in determining shear banding onsets emphasizes the proposed model as well-controlled in its ability to differentiate between relaxation and no relaxation in lipid monolayers.

The computational model also reproduces the expected post-onset shear banding behavior based on the stress-strain relationships for each case in simple shear. Specifically, for cases where the stress-strain relationship in simple shear is monotonic and exhibits no relaxation point, there is no instability in the material's shear deformations, shown in the insets in Fig 3 for Case 1 and neo-Hookean. In cases where the stress-strain relationship in simple shear is non-monotonic, such as Cases 2 and 3, distinct shear bands form in the material. This is visualized in Fig 3 inset snapshots as bands of high shear strain. Furthermore, the degree of non-monotonicity in the stress-strain response is found to significantly control how strong and persistent shear banding is. In Case 3, the shear bands that form are strong and persist in distinct bands over the course of the compression, as expected for its reaction force response with a strong relaxation behavior and lack of second elastic regime. In Case 2, however, the shear bands form with very low shear strain and dilute or diffuse into the rest of the material over the course of the compression, also as expected for its reaction force behavior with a weaker relaxation behavior followed by a quick turn to the second elastic regime. The difference between shear strain within the band to outside the band for Case 3 is 5 times as large than that of Case 2, further showcasing the difference in behavior of these two parameter sets.

We have identified an efficient model for lipid monolayers that, for the first time, can capture in-plane relaxation and its relation to folding in a controllable and tunable manner. Its extension to the realistic heterogeneous representation of

lipid monolayers will be presented next to further identify the mechanism inherent in the material model that separates folding and in-plane relaxation.

Figure 4. FE model built from FM images of DPPC:POPG 7:3 plus 2 mol% SP-B 9-25 peptide lipid monolayer (see Fig. 3). Significantly less localized shear strains are seen in FE model using the monotonic stress strain curve (Case 1 in Fig. 3, left), while strong shear bands occurring as shocklines form in the matrix for the non-monotonic stress-strain response, promoting condensed domain reorganization (Case 3 in Fig. 3, right).

Non-monotonic hyperelastic matrix driving shear bands that allow for in-plane relaxation via domain reorganization: heterogeneous lipid monolayers.

The FE model using a homogeneous representation of lipid monolayers is extended to incorporate the presence of condensed domains surrounded by a softer matrix. Specifically, we constructed a FE model starting with the lipid monolayer geometry obtained via a FM microscopy image of DPPC:POPG 7:3 plus 2 mol% SP-B 9-25 peptide lipid monolayer system at 30mN m^{-1} . This image was taken before onset of in-plane relaxation, where the domain organization is in powder structure, as seen in Fig 2 (37) (see Method section).

We then simulated the unilateral horizontal loading similar to the homogeneous case to mimic the compression process in Langmuir trough experiments. While the domains are modeled with the neo-Hookean material, the matrix is modeled using three cases as conducted on the homogeneous model in the previous section. For Case 1, where the system does not shear band in the homogeneous system, there are no shear bands forming in the matrix (Fig 4, left). For Case 3, shear bands form between the domains on diagonals in the form of strong localized regions of shear strain that allow for domains to break their hexagonal symmetry, coming closer in the lateral direction than the vertical (Fig 4, right). Note, the material within the shear bands of Case 3 is being deformed on the order of 10x as much as the most strained material between domains in Case 1, as seen in the maximum strain values of Fig 4. Case 2 also exhibits the emergence of shear bands, which dissolve over the course of the simulation similar to what is seen in the homogeneous case, with the final strain localization very similar to that of Case 1 (See Movie 2). The consistency of shear banding onset and behavior between the homogeneous and heterogeneous FE models suggests a robust nature of the proposed material model. In addition, following the localization of shear bands in Case 3 throughout compression supports our hypothesis that shear bands between domains may be an important underlying mechanism to in-plane relaxation in lipid monolayers.

The results show that the addition of condensed domains is not sufficient to impose shear bands in a material that does not shear band in a homogeneous case. On the other hand, simulations suggest that the capability of the matrix to relax in-plane load induced by the compression process, which can be tuned through our proposed constitutive model, play a critical role in the reorganization of condensed domains. These simulations with great tunability for the first time provide insightful information of how domains impact the formation and organization of shear bands and the mechanisms that dictate different modes of instability. They also enrich the current continuum model that is only applicable to folding lipid monolayers.

Model validation with experimental data: Analysis of domain morphology

In the Langmuir trough experiment, in-plane relaxation is evaluated by domain morphology via FM. To further confirm that our FE model can capture and tune between lipid monolayers that exhibit different instability modes, in this Section we provide a comparison to experimental results.

Figure 5. Validation against experimental data for DPPC:POPG 7:3 with and without 2 mol% SP-B 9-25 peptide system. Simulations without shear band formation in the matrix (Case 1) show the nearly hexagonal packing is maintained at high compression, highlighted with 2D image autocorrelations, where powder structure is present for both the experiment and FE model (left column). Simulations with strong shear band formation in the matrix (Case 3) show similar domain organization to that observed in in-plane relaxing experiments, also highlighted using 2D image autocorrelations (right column).

FE model captures in-plane relaxation signature from experimental images.

As presented in the Introduction, in-plane relaxation in the Langmuir trough experiments is characterized by the reorganization of domain morphology from powder structure to lines of condensed domains with broken organizational symmetry. This pattern is emphasized via image analysis, utilizing 2D autocorrelation as shown in Fig 2 for the DPPC:POPG 7:3 plus 2 mol% SP-B 9-25 peptide system. Specifically, as stated in the methods, the powder structure domain organization in the 2D autocorrelation can be characterized as a circle and ring for nearest neighbors with disordered long range spatial correlation, seen in the experimental system before folding (Fig 5 top, left). The in-plane relaxation organization can be characterized in the 2D autocorrelation as persistent stripes from short to long range, seen in the experimental case of in-plane relaxation (Fig 5 top, right). The same approach is applied to analyze the domain morphology from FE models (see Fig 4) of the two corresponding heterogeneous lipid monolayers in which the matrix is modeled with Case 1 (no shear bands) and Case 3 (strong shear bands). Results for the domain morphology in Fig 5 show that the resultant autocorrelation for Case 1 (no shear bands) has the characteristic circle and ring that indicates powder structure. This indicates a recreation of the local experimental in-plane morphology of a folding monolayer. In direct comparison, the resultant autocorrelation for Case 3 (strong shear bands) has the characteristic persistent stripes from short to long range, recreating the experimental morphology of in-plane relaxation (Fig 5). This suggests that strong shear banding in the matrix is sufficient to capture the experimental domain morphology of the DPPC:POPG 7:3 plus 2 mol% SP-B 9-25 peptide system. Our FE models for the first time can capture the experimental data for both folding and in-plane relaxation, providing a mechanism for tuning between the in-plane morphology of two instability modes.

Figure 6. Progression of the morphology of condensed domains obtained from FE models of lipid monolayers constructed from FM images and analyzed with 2D image correlation. Three cases for material model (see Fig. 3) for the soft matrix are used. For each case, the aggregate reaction force of the left boundary nodes is plotted against the nominal stretch, with insets showcasing transient morphologies analyzed with 2D autocorrelations. In the initial elastic regime of the compression, all cases show nearly hexagonal packing in their 2D autocorrelation. For Case 1, no shear banding in the matrix leads to no significant changes in the near hexagonal packing of condensed domains, as shown by the corresponding 2D autocorrelations. For Case 2, an in-plane relaxation morphology develops in the relaxation regime but then converts back to hexagonal packing when the reaction force increases again. For Case 3, at the critical nominal stretch shown in red, strong and persistent shear bands develop. This leads to 2D autocorrelations that develop to match the signature of in-plane relaxation in experimental cases (Fig 5).

Progression of autocorrelation signature throughout compression can be tuned with material properties.

While Fig 5 showcases the endpoint of the simulations, we can also gain valuable insights by assessing the aggregate reaction force measurement and transient domain organization over the course of the compression. Overall, the reaction force response of the heterogeneous simulations mimics the response of those without domains as seen in Fig 3: Case 1 exhibits a monotonic stress-strain relationship, Case 2 exhibits a non-monotonic relationship with a weaker and shorter relaxation, and Case 3 exhibits a strong and persistent relaxation. What is especially interesting, however, is the progression of the autocorrelation signature for each of these cases. Case 1 exhibits a slight loss of symmetry at its inflection point, while returning to a stretched powder structure oval signature as the compression develops further and reaction force continues to increase. Case 3 provides a clear example of a 2D autocorrelation morphing from powder structure to the signature of in-plane relaxation. The circle and ring signature steadily loses its symmetry as it converts into persistent lines. The most dynamic transient morphing is shown in Case 2. With a matrix material that forms shear band strain localizations which then quickly dissolve, Case 2 exhibits a stronger loss of symmetry than that of Case 1 immediately after the onset of shear bands, closely resembling the autocorrelation signature of Case 3 (strong shear banding). However, towards the end of the simulation, as the shear bands dissolve, the autocorrelations quickly revert to a stretched powder structure, with the endpoint autocorrelation signature extremely similar to that of Case 1 (no shear banding)

In summary, through exploring a new hyperelastic model for lipid monolayers integrated with validated FE simulations, we are able to impose and modulate shear bands in both homogeneous thin sheets and thin sheets with stiff inclusions mimicking condensed domains. With an experimental lipid monolayer FM-derived domain organization as the initial morphology, we are able to compare resultant deformed morphologies directly to those of the experimental systems and assess the local domain packing structures. From the quantification of these packing structures in the form of 2D autocorrelations, we find that the formation and persistence of shear bands in the matrix between domains are sufficient in reproducing the in-plane relaxation signature from experiments. And with the dissipation of such shear bands, that reproduction is lost and the domain packing structure returns to hexagonal structure. The unique strength of a hyperelastic material with a non-monotonic shear stress-strain relationship is its ability to impose a temporary relaxation. This model in particular is also built with strong tunability, showcased by its ability to capture not only hexagonal packing

(no shear banding in Case 1) and in-plane relaxation (strong shear banding in Case 3), but also the morphing of domain packing structures (weak, transient shear banding in Case 2). This mimics the experimental system, as lipid monolayers can exhibit other modes of collapse between folding and in-plane relaxation.

CONCLUSIONS

This work develops an effective elastic framework that explains in-plane morphologies of lipid monolayer instabilities by incorporating shear strain localization in the form of shear bands. To probe our hypothesis that shear bands allow for domain reorganization in the case of in-plane relaxation, we first establish a constitutive model that tunes between strong, weak, and no shear banding. Our developed constitutive model is then utilized in FE simulations to study how shear bands in a soft matrix localize in the presence of FM-derived domain morphology. The domain packing as a result of shear banding is validated against experimental signatures via 2D autocorrelation quantification, thereby concluding that shear bands as the result of a non-monotonic shear stress-strain relationship are sufficient in capturing in-plane relaxation domain morphology. Furthermore, by assessing the autocorrelation signatures throughout the compression process in the three cases of strong, weak, and no shear banding, transient modes of surface instabilities between folding and in-plane relaxation are captured. These results show the effectiveness of our model to unify different instability modes observed experimentally in lipid monolayers, in particular the strong correlation with the general experimental diagram where surface instabilities can be tuned in various lipid compositions. Further research probing the smaller-scale underlying mechanisms behind this effective behavior can give way to a multiscale understanding of macroscopic surface instabilities. While the focus in the paper is lipid monolayers, this work is also applicable to understanding surface instabilities in other thin sheet systems.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental lipid monolayer compression measurements. Experimental data used for comparison and validation to our developed computational model utilize fluorescence microscopy (FM) micrographs of two lipid monolayer compositions deposited and compressed on a Langmuir trough, as published previously in Pocivavsek, et al, 2008 (37). The two compositions shown in figures 2 and 5 are 7:3 DPPC:POPG (folding) and 7:3 DPPC:POPG with 10 wt% SP-B 9–25 (in-plane relaxation) at 25°C. As described in the published methods, the solutions were diluted to obtain spreading solutions of concentration 0.1 mg ml^{-1} . The fluorescent probe used for visualization at 0.5 mol% with FM was Texas Red 1,2-dihexadecanoyl-*sn*-glycerol-3-phosphoethanolamine (TR-DHPE) (Molecular Probes, Eugene, OR). These two samples were deposited on ultrapure water under ultra high purity argon to minimize oxidative damage. The instrument used to collect this data was a custom-made Teflon trough equipped with two Teflon barriers whose motions were precisely controlled for symmetric uniaxial lateral compression with a linear speed of 0.1 mm s^{-1} . A stationary Wilhelmy balance (Riegler and Kirstein, Berlin, Germany) was used to measure surface pressure.

Image analysis. We can describe the spatial distribution of regions showing high (bright matrix) and low (dark condensed domains) levels of fluorescence using an adaptation of previously published methods (37). This method begins with filtering to remove high and low frequency noise associated with nonuniform illumination. Then, a 2D autocorrelation of the entire FM image is conducted, followed by a 2D Fourier power spectrum of this autocorrelation to give the structure factor. This structure factor gives the average nearest neighbor packing for all the domains in the image, where a circle indicates powder structure, an oval indicates a stretching of that lattice, and the formation of distinct nodes indicate symmetry breaking of the stretching of the lattice (37). This method gives the average packing over many domains, however, in this work we choose to showcase more local domain organization, since our FE models utilize a portion of the FM micrograph morphology. We do this by conducting 2D autocorrelations on cropped FM images from these samples. These autocorrelations indicate the rate of decay in positional correlation between bright and dark regions in the image. This means the signature at the center of the autocorrelation refers to average nearest neighbor spacing, while the structures formed away from the center refers to spacing farther away. In most autocorrelation figures in this work, we bring focus to the nearest neighbor morphology by adding a red semi-transparent circle or oval.

Material model. In this work, a hyperelastic model is proposed by developing the model of Seki and Atluri (66) to describe and model the behavior of a lipid monolayer matrix, given as

$$\psi = \hat{\psi}(\mathbf{C}) = \frac{C_1(\bar{I}_1-3)}{[1+C_2(\bar{I}_1-3)]} + C_3(\bar{I}_1-3)^2 + \frac{K}{2}(J-1)^2, \quad (1)$$

where $\bar{I}_1 := tr\bar{\mathbf{C}} = J^{-2/3}tr\mathbf{C}$ is defined as the first invariant of $\bar{\mathbf{C}}$, with $tr(\bullet)$ the trace of a tensor, K is the bulk modulus, C_1 , C_2 , and C_3 are material parameters. Note that $C_1 = \mu/2$, where μ is shear modulus.

From this strain energy function, the constitutive model can be derived (see details in Appendix 1):

$$\sigma = \left\{ \frac{2C_1}{1+C_2(\bar{I}_1-3)} - \frac{2C_1C_2(\bar{I}_1-3)}{[1+C_2(\bar{I}_1-3)]^2} + 4C_3(\bar{I}_1-3) \right\} J^{-5/3} \left(\mathbf{B} - \frac{I_1}{3}\mathbf{I} \right) + K(J-1)\mathbf{I}, \quad (2)$$

Loss of ellipticity analysis for shear banding. A 2D shear band can be characterized mathematically as an area, surrounded by shocklines, where the shear strain is significantly higher than outside. As described in Seki and Atluri (66), there exists for some $\gamma_1 \neq \gamma_2$ the following inequality given by Abeyaratne and Knowles 1989 (67) where shocklines exist in plane strain incompressible materials

$$[\tau(\gamma_1) - \tau(\gamma_2)][\gamma_1 - \gamma_2] \leq 0. \quad (3)$$

This means that loss of ellipticity occurs when the slope of the shear stress-shear strain relationship transitions from positive to negative, at some critical shear strain, $\gamma_{S,C}$. The loss of ellipticity condition is used to determine the critical point where a uniaxial compression experiences shear deformation by assessing the following equation for the equivalent amount of shear strain in a two-dimensional case

$$\gamma_S^2 = \text{trace}(\mathbf{B}) - 2, \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{B} is the left Cauchy-Green deformation tensor for a uniaxial compression of a quasi-incompressible material in terms of λ_N , nominal stretch (L/L_0), given by the following equation

$$\mathbf{B} := \overline{\mathbf{F}\mathbf{F}^T} = \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_N & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_N^{-1} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_N & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_N^{-1} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_N^2 & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_N^{-2} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (5)$$

Thus, loss of ellipticity occurs when $\mathcal{L}(\lambda_N) = 0$ at some critical nominal stretch $\lambda_{N,C}$, where

$$\mathcal{L}(\lambda_N) = \text{trace}(\mathbf{B}) - 2 - \gamma_{S,C}^2 = \lambda_N^2 + \frac{1}{\lambda_N^2} - 2 - \gamma_{S,C}^2, \quad (6)$$

Finite element simulations. We continue previously developed methods for replicating the uniaxial lateral compression of lipid monolayers using numerical modeling (39), integrating principles of nonlinear, large deformation solid mechanics with finite element (FE) analysis. FE simulations are implemented using the commercial software package Abaqus/Explicit 2021 (Dassault Systèmes Americas Corp., Waltham, MA). The constitutive model is implemented into Abaqus/Explicit by writing the user subroutine VUMAT. We use two thin sheet models: a homogeneous model composed of a single material and a heterogeneous model composed of domains and a surrounding matrix of two respective materials. These models are built with the following unit system: length of micrometer in reference to the scale of FM micrographs utilized in the heterogeneous model (37), modulus unit of MPa in reference to experimental surface pressure measurements (37, 39, 68), and a unit mass of 10^{-9} g, in reference to the 1 g cm^{-3} density of water, for a dynamic explicit solver. For all matrix materials, the compressibility is dictated by the bulk modulus $K = 200 \text{ MPa}$. This value is determined by the relation $K = 4C_1(1 + \nu)/3(1 - 2\nu)$, where Poisson's ratio, $\nu \sim 0.495$ for a quasi-incompressible material.

Homogeneous model: A $10 \times 10 \times 1$ size thin square is meshed with 10,000 uniform two-dimensional plane strain shell elements (CPE4R, 4 node bilinear quadrilateral, reduced integration, with hourglass control).

Heterogeneous model: FM image of a lipid monolayer before in-plane relaxation, of composition 7:3 DPPC:POPG with 10 wt% SP-B 9–25, at 20C and a surface pressure of 30mN m⁻¹ as published previously (37), is imported into the Simpleware ScanIP software (Synopsys, Inc., Mountain View, CA) to segment out the domains from the matrix. This is brought into ABAQUS and converted into a sketch, which is then partitioned into a 350x350x1 size thin square. The domains and matrix are then meshed with 149482 total two-dimensional plane strain shell elements (97% CPE4R, 4 node bilinear quadrilateral, reduced integration, with hourglass control; 3% CPE3, 3 node linear triangle, reduced integration, with hourglass control). In addition, we provide approximately 60 units of excess matrix surrounding the domains to cushion the dynamic effects at the boundaries of the simulation, as seen in the initial morphology in Fig 4. The matrix is given the material property described previously in the methods. The condensed domains are made of a neo-Hookean material with the same thickness and density, but approximately 100x stiffer than the matrix, with the material equation as follows, where $C_{10} = 100$ and $K = 4000$. Note that $C_{10} = \mu/2$, where μ is shear modulus.

$$\psi_D = C_{10}(\bar{I}_1 - 3) + \frac{K}{2}(J - 1)^2, \quad (7)$$

Boundary conditions: The use of plane strain in both models enforces a 2D geometric constraint. These models are then subjected to equal compression from both left and right boundaries to represent the loading condition in the experimental Langmuir trough setup. There are no boundary conditions on the top and bottom boundaries of the models' geometries. In both models, there is a general contact interaction property applied to all material with itself, to prevent unrealistic permeation of multiple elements. In the heterogeneous model, this same general contact interaction property is applied at the boundaries where the domains and matrix meet, preventing permeation of domains into the matrix, or vice versa.

Post processing: While simulations are run, data is recorded at regular intervals, providing frames for regular points along the compression of the model. As the rate of compression is not constant to avoid dynamic effects, compression is measured by nominal stretch, $\lambda_N = L/L_0$, where L is the width of the FE model. To measure the effective stress and relaxation of the FE models as a whole, aggregate reaction force of the left boundary of each model is collected at each frame of the compression. This aggregate is calculated via a summation of the lateral component of the reaction force over all nodes of the left boundary. Due to the symmetric loading of the system, the right boundary could also be used, as it would exhibit approximately an equal and opposite reaction force response. To visualize shear strain localization in FE models and monitor shear band formation and behavior, the state dependent variable defined in the VUMAT that tracks and updates the shear strain, γ_S (further explained in Appendix 1 and Eq 12), is plotted on the deformed geometry of the models over the course of the compression. In Fig 3, Case 3 and Fig 4, comparative visualization is assisted by manually selecting min/max limits for shear strain values. The characteristic that defines shear bands is the difference between the shear strain within the localized shear band vs. outside of the band. A strong shear band has a large difference in shear strain, while a weaker one has a small difference.

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APPENDIX

1. Constitutive model implementation.

Basic kinematics. A lipid monolayer is assumed to be a continuum body. Consider an arbitrary material particle in the reference configuration \mathcal{B}_0 of the continuum body at the reference time $t = 0$. The position of the particle is characterized by its position vector \mathbf{X} . This particle transforms to a position \mathbf{x} in the current configuration \mathcal{B} at time t following the motion $\chi(\mathbf{X}, t)$. The deformation gradient tensor is defined as $\mathbf{F} := \partial\mathbf{x}/\partial\mathbf{X}$. The determinant of \mathbf{F} is denoted by $J := \det \mathbf{F} > 0$. The right and left Cauchy–Green deformation tensors are introduced as $\mathbf{C} := \mathbf{F}^T \mathbf{F}$ and $\mathbf{B} := \mathbf{F} \mathbf{F}^T$, respectively. The spatial velocity gradient tensor is given as $\mathbf{L} := \dot{\mathbf{F}} \mathbf{F}^{-1}$, with $(\dot{\bullet})$ the material time derivative of a quantity (\bullet) . \mathbf{F} is split into an isochoric part $J^{1/3} \mathbf{I}$ and a volumetric part $\bar{\mathbf{F}}$, i.e., $\mathbf{F} = J^{1/3} \bar{\mathbf{F}}$, where \mathbf{I} is the 2nd-order identity tensor, and $\bar{\mathbf{F}}$ is the modified deformation gradient tensor. Thus, the modified right and left Cauchy–Green deformation tensors are correspondingly introduced as $\bar{\mathbf{C}} := \bar{\mathbf{F}}^T \bar{\mathbf{F}}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{B}} := \bar{\mathbf{F}} \bar{\mathbf{F}}^T$, respectively.

Constitutive relations. The Helmholtz free energy density function ψ is assumed to exist, which is defined per unit reference volume. Within the large deformation framework, the free energy density is assumed to be a function of the right Cauchy–Green deformation tensor, i.e., $\psi = \hat{\psi}(\mathbf{C})$. In this work, we focus on the experimental state where a lipid monolayer exhibits the solid phase, where the monolayer shows quasi-incompressible characteristics. To separately describe the isochoric and volumetric contributions, the free energy density ψ is decomposed into two parts, i.e.,

$$\psi = \psi_{iso} + \psi_{vol}, \text{ with } \psi_{iso} = \hat{\psi}_{iso}(\bar{\mathbf{C}}) \text{ and } \psi_{vol} = \hat{\psi}_{vol}(J), \quad (8)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{C}}$ and J can be expressed as functions of \mathbf{C} , i.e., $\bar{\mathbf{C}} = J^{-2/3} \mathbf{C}$ and $J = (\det \mathbf{C})^{1/2}$, respectively.

Under the isothermal conditions, the Clausius–Planck inequality is expressed as

$$\mathcal{D}_{int} = \mathbf{S} \cdot \frac{\dot{\mathbf{C}}}{2} - \dot{\psi} = \left(\mathbf{S} - 2 \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \mathbf{C}} \right) \cdot \frac{\dot{\mathbf{C}}}{2} \geq 0, \quad (9)$$

where $(\bullet) \cdot (\bullet)$ denotes a double contraction, \mathbf{S} represents the second Piola–Kirchhoff stress tensor, and \mathcal{D}_{int} is the non-negative internal dissipation. Since \mathbf{C} can be chosen arbitrarily, to fulfill the inequality, one has

$$\mathbf{S} = 2 \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \mathbf{C}}. \quad (10)$$

The Cauchy stress σ can be calculated as

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{J} \mathbf{F} \mathbf{S} \mathbf{F}^T = \frac{2}{J} \mathbf{F} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \mathbf{C}} \mathbf{F}^T. \quad (11)$$

Constitutive relation in simple shear. For describing the shear banding of monolayers, a new invariant is defined to measure the amount of shear strain in simple shear (see (66) for more details), i.e.,

$$\gamma_S^2 = \bar{I}_1 - 3. \quad (12)$$

The free energy density can be rewritten as a function of γ and J , i.e., $\psi = \hat{\psi}(\gamma, J)$. The shear stress in simple shear is calculated as

$$\tau = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \gamma} = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \bar{I}_1} \frac{\partial \bar{I}_1}{\partial \gamma} = 2\gamma \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \bar{I}_1}. \quad (13)$$

Figure S1. Depiction of tunability and 3-regime form of shear banding material model. A) The shear stress-shear strain relationship in the case of simple shear is plotted for 7 different parameter sets to showcase the tunability of the chosen constitutive model, using Eq 14. C_1 (blue) is shown to alter the slope of the first elastic regime. C_2 (yellow) is shown to alter the critical shear strain or point of relaxation. C_3 (red) is shown to alter the slope of the second elastic regime. B) The shear stress-shear strain relationship in the case of simple shear is plotted for a representative parameter set to showcase the 3-regime form of the model when it is non-monotonic. The first region (blue) is considered the first elastic regime. The second region (yellow) is considered the relaxation regime, the presence of which allows for shear banding to take place. The third region (red) is considered the second elastic regime. When a parameter set creates a monotonic relationship, there is no relaxation regime.

2. Tunability of non-monotonic material model

Taking the model described in the methods, the stress-strain relationship in simple shear can be calculated through Eq 13 (where $\tau(\gamma)$ is stress in simple shear as a function of γ_S , the amount of shear strain in simple shear), which can be derived as

$$\tau(\gamma_S) = 2\gamma_S \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \bar{I}_1} = 2\gamma \left[\frac{C_1}{1+C_2\gamma_S^2} - \frac{C_1 C_2 \gamma_S^2}{(1+C_2\gamma_S^2)^2} + 2C_3\gamma_S^2 \right], \quad (14)$$

We have chosen three parameter sets to act as typical cases for this model (Case 1: $C_1=1$, $C_2=5$, $C_3=0.5$; Case 2: $C_1=1$, $C_2=5$, $C_3=0.1$; Case 3: $C_1=1$, $C_2=10$, $C_3=0.001$) as well as a neo-Hookean case ($C_1=1$, $C_2=0$, $C_3=0$), results for all of which are shown in Fig 3. These cases were chosen to best showcase the range of behavior this model can capture. In Cases 2 and 3, there are inflection points where the stress-strain relationship in simple shear changes sign, giving a local maximum that is not given in Case 1 or the neo-Hookean case. Cases 2 and 3 differ in that the local maximum in which Case 2 has a larger shear stress and shear strain value. In addition, Case 2 has a second inflection point where the slope transitions from negative to positive with only a small change in shear strain.

3. Comparison of analytical and numerical loss of ellipticity.

The results of the loss of ellipticity calculation from Eq 6 for all typical cases with a $\gamma_{S,C}$ are shown in the subplots of Fig 3. The $\lambda_{N,C}$ values for Case 2 and Case 3 are 0.874 and 0.914, respectively. Using the homogeneous FE model built with the constitutive model as described in the methods, we characterize the effective behavior of the material through recording aggregate reaction force on the left boundary as a function of nominal stretch, λ_N . The point where the reaction force drops is the critical nominal stretch, or $\lambda_{N,C}$. As shown in Fig 3, this computational critical point agrees with the analytical onset of relaxation, suggesting the constitutive model carries well into the computational model. For the parameter sets that do not analytically provide a relaxation point, such as Case 1 and neo-Hookean, plotted in Fig 3, the resultant computational result shows no drop in reaction force, showcasing the ability for the analytical solution to differentiate between relaxation and no relaxation.

Movies 1-3. FE model built from FM images of DPPC:POPG 7:3 plus 2 mol% SP-B 9-25 peptide lipid monolayer (see Fig. 4). Shear strain from Eq 12 is plotted as a heat map for all three videos, with a manually selected minimum and maximum, as shown in the legend of each video. Movie 1 shows the compression where the matrix has the parameters of Case 1 (no shear banding); Movie 2 has the parameters of Case 2 (weak shear banding); Movie 3 has the parameters of Case 3 (strong shear banding).